

RCI - LIMOGES PORCELAIN

GESTURE SEGEMENTATION

I. PLASTER TURNING ON WHEEL

1. INSTALLATION OF FORMWORK
 - 1.1. MEASURING AND MARKING REFERENCE POINTS
 - 1.2. WORKSPACE AND MATERIAL PREPARATION
 - 1.3. CHECKING MEASUREMENTS AND MARKING REFERENCE POINTS
 - 1.4. SOAPING THE TURNING PLATE
 - 1.5. FIXING THE FORMWORK TO THE TURNING PLATE
 - 1.5.1. POSITIONING THE FORMWORK ON THE PLATE
 - 1.5.2. CLOSING THE FORMWORK WITH CLIPS
 - 1.5.3. COILING
 - 1.5.4. FIXING THE WORKFORM
 - 1.6. POURING THE PLASTER INTO THE FORMWORK

2. PLASTER MIXTURE PREPARATION
 - 2.1. MIXING PLASTER POWDER AND WATER
 - 2.2. STIRRING THE PLASTER MIXTURE
 - 2.3. REMOVING AIR BUBBLES
 - 2.4. PLASTER MIXTURE THICKENING

3. PLASTER TURNING ON WHEEL
 - 3.1. PREPARING THE TURNING TOOLS
 - 3.2. CHECKING PLASTER CONSISTENCY
 - 3.3. FORMWORK REMOVAL
 - 3.4. FINDING AND MARKING THE CENTRE OF THE PIECE.
 - 3.5. PLASTER TURNING (CARVING with trimming, turning or carving tools
("tournassins")
 - 3.5.1. CARVING UPPER LEVEL
 - 3.5.2. CARVING MEDIUM LEVEL

- 3.5.3. CARVING LOWEL LEVEL
- 3.5.4. MEASUREMENTS (at various times along the process)
- 3.5.5. MARKING REFERENCE POINTS (at various times along the process)
- 3.5.6. TOOL CLEANING (at various times along the process)
- 3.6. SMOOTHING THE SURFACE WITH A FLAT SCRAPER
- 3.7. CARVING ADJUSTMENTS
- 3.8. SANDING
 - 3.8.1. SANDING WITH MEDIUM GRIT SANDPAPER
 - 3.8.2. SANDING WITH FINE GRIT SANDPAPER

II. **SLIP CASTING** (Porcelain forming technique)

- 1. CENTRING THE MOULD ON THE WHIRLER
- 2. POURING PORCELAIN SLIP INTO THE MOULD
- 3. CASTING TIME (or Setting time) (10')
- 4. POURING OUT THE EXCESS SLIP or DRAINING:
 - 4.1. TITLING THE MOULD OR PLACING THE MOULD AT AN ANGLE (on the slip casting draining table)
 - 4.2. TURNING THE MOULD UPSIDE DOWN (on the slip casting draining table)
- 5. DEMOULDING
 - 5.1. TRIMMING AWAY THE EXCESS SLIP FROM THE OUTSIDE OF THE MOULD (with a sharp scalpel)
 - 5.2. REMOVAL OF THE UPPER PART OF THE MOULD (“Bride”)
 - 5.3. TURNING THE MOULD OVER AND SHACKING IT
 - 5.4. OPENING THE MOULD
 - 5.5. TRIMMING AWAY THE EXCESS SLIP FROM OF THE INTERIOR OF THE MOULD (with a sharp scalpel)
 - 5.6. TAPPING THE MOULD (with the fist)
 - 5.7. TURNING THE MOULD OVER

5.8. DEMOULDING THE PIECE (on the hand)

5.9. RECLOSING THE MOULD

III. **JOINING THE HANDLE**

1. CUTTING OFF THE HANDLE ENDS

2. ATTACHING THE HANDLES

2.1. POSITIONING + FIXING OF HANDLE #1 (Porcelain glue):

2.1.1. Dipping in the handle in porcelain glue (slip + few drops of vinegar).

2.1.2. Positioning the handle (perpendicular to the cup base)

2.1.3. Sticking the handle to the body of the cup.

2.1.4. Moistening the handle area (with sponge)

2.2. ATTACHING THE HANDLE #2 (SOLID TOOL: Wooden modelling tool)

2.3. ATTACHING THE HANDLE #3 (SOFT TOOL: Brush)

2.3.1. Wet the brush.

2.3.2. Discharge excess water onto a workpiece.

2.3.3. Take some glue with the brush.

2.3.4. Filling the joints (between the handle and the body of the cup) with slip

2.3.5. Smoothing the joints with the brush.

IV. **FETTLING or REMOVAL OF SEAM LINES**

1. TRIMMING AWAY SEAM LINES (or mould marks) WITH A SOLID TOOL (with a sharp scalpel)

2. SPONGE FINISHING:

2.1. FINISHING (SMOOTHING) WITH SOFT TOOL #1 (Finishing sponge)

2.2. FINISHING (SMOOTHING) WITH SOFT TOOL #2 (Flat rectangular sponge)

2.3. FINISHING (SMOOTHING) WITH SOFT TOOL #3 (Thin sponge with wooden handle)

2.4. FINISHING (SMOOTHING) WITH SOFT TOOL #4 (Flat rectangular sponge)